

BAYESIAN STATISTICS IN HOMOEOPATHY: A REVIEW OF PAST, PRESENT AND FUTURE

Rakhshanda Ayoub Department of Homoeopathic Repertory, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital, Pune -Satara Road-411043.

Jyoti Deepak Patil*Department of Homoeopathic Repertory, Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University), Homoeopathic Medical College and Hospital, Pune -Satara Road-411043.

Email: jyoti.patil@bharatividyaapeeth.edu

ABSTRACT

The addition of symptoms to our Materia medica is based on their absolute frequency. In systems dependent on experience, such as Homoeopathy, confirmation bias is a significant source of misleading data. There are false entries in our repertories as a result of this absolute occurrence in successful circumstances. We may address these issues and give Homoeopathy a scientific name by using Bayes theorem. The Bayes theorem contrasts the general population with the population that benefits from a particular Homoeopathic remedy. We must be aware of how common Homoeopathic symptoms are both in the population treated by the medication and in all other communities. The likelihood ratio is used to express the relationship between these two numbers (LR). This study determines that by creating a new standard for adding to or eliminating entries from the repertory, we likely require a different method of handling statistical uncertainty than in hypothesis testing. Symptoms need to be described more precisely. It is important to validate the accuracy of our scales for measuring cure.

KEYWORDS:

Bayesian Theorem, Homoeopathy, Likelihood ratio, Repertory.

INTRODUCTION:

Homoeopathy has provided individualized medicine for over two centuries. Aside from RCT, the recent demand for personalized research provides an excellent opportunity to favor other EBM methods for improving knowledge in Homoeopathic Materia Medica and Repertories. Unconsciously, the Homoeopathic method is based on the sound scientific theory of conditional probability, but our repertories are not. Expert advice is valuable, but it is susceptible to bias and the influence of chance. The impact of chance could be reduced by collecting more cases from different doctors. If we want to use our experience in a cutting-edge way, we must understand the prevalence of Homoeopathic symptoms not only in the population cured by the medicine but also in the remaining populations.

Homeopathic medicines should be handled individually. Homeopathic doctors use symptoms and characteristics seen in cases responding well to a specific medicine to select the same medicine in a new patient. Such data are recorded in the homeopathic repertory. Until recently, little attention was paid to the influence of chance in such data. Data collection was insufficiently systematic and the theoretical background was weak. This could become a threat to the reliability of our most important instrument, especially now repertories are easily updated by the use of computers.

The scientific validity of homoeopathy is not weak as many people think. However, the present criteria for accepting a symptom as an indication for a Homoeopathic medicine are fundamentally wrong. According to Bayes theorem these criteria should be based on relative occurrence instead of absolute occurrence. Bayesian theorem can be applied in retrospective research and in the validation of Materia medica with successful cases using consensus procedure.

Bayes' theorem provides a theoretical basis for translating experience into knowledge. The knowledge of homeopathic doctors is built upon implicit comparisons of the prevalence of a symptom in a population-subgroup responding well to a specific homeopathic medicine (medicine population) and the prevalence of the same symptom in the remainder of the population.

Homeopathic doctors must be involved in validating homeopathic Materia Medica and Repertories because their cases are the basic material. This is possible if we are familiar with basic principles of science and statistics. We must realize that their practice experience has scientific value if assessed properly. This can form the basis of drug validation and evidence so generated across the globe by multiple prescribers can be stronger and more meaningful than present Rates.

This study is going to include extensive research into the basic principles of present process of rubric /symptom grading in repertories which is based on absolute numbers than relative numbers. Relative grading using absolute numbers apparently gives impression of some absolute truth, without reflecting statistical uncertainties and measurement bias, and how several methods of Bayesian assessment of symptoms are demonstrated so that we can achieve a tremendous scientific improvement of homeopathy within a limited amount of time. Within ten years, we could know LR's of characteristic symptoms for our most frequently prescribed homeopathic medicines. Applying the formula that goes with Bayesian theory we will be able to tell the patient: "Based on the symptoms you gave me I expect the chance.

Homeopathy and its current methods of scientific evidence:

Homeopathy has a communication problem. An important problem is that of incommensurability of terminology; we often use a different language from conventional colleagues.¹ We talk of 'remedy picture' instead of diagnosis. We value peculiar symptoms highly while conventional doctors ignore them. In our secret language, we refer to Hahnemann's aphorism 153 (referring to peculiar symptoms) to indicate why a certain medicine was prescribed. We use an unusual term, 'pathognomonic' to indicate that symptoms typical of a disease are unimportant, the opposite to conventional medicine. Our alternative language is necessary to express something that is missing in conventional medicine, but it creates problems when trying to communicate with conventional colleagues. How can we convince others that we must prescribe on 'remedy picture' rather than a diagnosis when we can offer nothing but experience to support this assertion?

Several renowned epidemiologists stated that the proof for homeopathy is not inferior to the proof for conventional medicine.² Others state that homeopathy is a placebo effect.³⁻⁵ Clearly, there is subjectivity involved in the interpretation of scientific evidence. A major problem is the plausibility of homeopathy's mechanism of action. Part of the scientific community acknowledges that scientific proof in randomized controlled trials (RCTs) and meta-analysis for homeopathy is not inferior to proof for conventional medicine, but that must be due to false positive findings.⁶ This makes homeopathy an interesting case for evaluating the scientific method.⁷

Which answer would you prefer: "This medicine works better than a placebo", or: "I estimate the chance that this medicine will work in your case to be 60%"?

These two answers reflect a two-and-a-half-century lasting dispute between two statistical methods, 'classical' and Bayesian. The first is regarded to be more scientific, the latter played a major part in solving many of history's most important problems.⁸ Nowadays many computer programs incorporate Bayes' theorem to handle experiential knowledge. Because RCT evidence does not allow other conclusions, the patient can only expect a yes-or-no statement about the efficacy of conventional medicines. But this answer might still be false in this particular case. Other factors, like correct diagnosis, genetic susceptibility and comorbidity, also determine if the medicine works.⁸

The diagnostic process preceding the prescription is Bayesian and renders the probability of a specific diagnosis. Bayesian philosophy is about learning from past experience, e.g., about characteristics of patients responding well to specific medicines. Like a medical diagnosis, the choice of a homeopathic medicine is a Bayesian process.

How can Randomised Controlled Trials (RCT) change our beliefs? The study states that the fact that they do RCTs update prior beliefs to different posterior beliefs is explained by Bayesian philosophy. Crucial points in Bayesian analysis include setting the first prior expectation right and sequential updating of the prior in the light of new evidence.⁹ Bayesian analysis depends highly on the evidence

included. RCT evidence can only falsify the placebo hypothesis, it cannot indicate which mechanism of action could be responsible for an intrinsic effect and therefore cannot overturn existing beliefs.

Systematic Mistakes in the Homoeopathic Repertories:

Every Homoeopathic practitioner has some doubts about Homoeopathic repertories. We know that many larger rubrics (frequently occurring symptoms) are unreliable, especially because they contain all “polychrests” (the most prescribed medicines). As a result, computer-Repertories offer the possibility to exclude polychrests from repertorization, but this solution is too rigorous: Frequently occurring symptoms can also indicate polychrests.¹⁰ The problem is caused by a systematic mistake in adding Repertory-entries.¹¹ A medicine is added to a repertory rubric if it is seen in a proving or a cured case if it is seen repeatedly the grading of medicine will be increased to italics or bold type. The problem is that we prescribe some medicines very frequently, some less frequently, and some seldom. This does not influence the acceptance as a repertory-entry, nor the grading of the medicine. Intuitively, we can understand that this is not correct.

A Committee of the Dutch Association of Homoeopathic Physicians is trying to validate *Materia Medica* by evaluating successful cases. These cases are presented and assessed by a group of experimental homoeopathic physicians to provide indications about prevalence of symptoms related to particular homoeopathic medicines. The next logical question is whether epidemiological techniques can be applied to them.

Ten Dutch homeopathic doctors, who recorded prospectively all cases during more than three years and checked the presence of six homeopathic symptoms in every new patient, conducted a prospective assessment of six homeopathic symptoms in every new patient. They also recorded the results of each prescribed medicine. In the end 4,094 patients entered the study and 4,072 prescriptions were evaluated. Comparing the prevalence of a symptom in a population that responds well to a specific medicine with the prevalence of the symptom in the remainder of the population renders the Likelihood Ratio (LR) of this symptom. If $LR > 1$, the symptom indicates the corresponding medicine. The findings confirm the most well-known – and accepted - entries of Kent’s repertory, but are different in more than half of the other entries.¹²

An assessment of the Likelihood Ratio (LR) of homeopathic symptoms started June 2004. Eleven doctors record the presence of six symptoms in every new patient. The symptoms are: ‘Diarrhoea from anticipation’, ‘Fear of death’, ‘Grinding teeth during sleep’, ‘Herpes lips and ‘Loquacity’. Prescribed medicines were also recorded and each doctor kept track of the results using a specified Glasgow Homeopathic Hospital Outcome Scale (GHHOS). After 15 months, in September 2005, an intermediate assessment was performed. At that time 1634 patients had been included and 1049 prescriptions evaluated. For calculating LR values we used all outcomes of 2-4 on the GHHOS scale.^{11,13}

It was concluded that; Kent’s Repertory has serious flaws. Frequently used medicines are over-rated, seldom-used medicines are under-rated. There is no clear system, so we have to overcome the problem by proper assessment of the prevalence of symptoms in populations responding to homeopathic medicines.¹¹

Improving Homoeopathic practice using Bayes’ theorem and likelihood ratio:

Homeopathic medicines should be handled individually, the doctor must often choose between a large number of medicines for the same condition. The medicine should fit the ‘type’ of person, according to specific symptoms and characteristics. Homeopathic doctors use symptoms and characteristics seen in cases responding well to a specific medicine to select the same medicine for a new patient. Such data are recorded in the homeopathic repertory, until recently, little attention was paid to the influence of chance in such data. Data collection was insufficiently systematic and the theoretical background was weak. This could become a threat to the reliability of our most important instrument, especially now repertories are easily updated by the use of computers.

Bayes' theorem provides a theoretical basis for translating experience into knowledge. The knowledge of homeopathic doctors is built upon implicit comparisons of the prevalence of a symptom in a population-subgroup responding well to a specific homeopathic medicine (medicine population) and the prevalence of the same symptom in the remainder of the population.¹² Bayes theorem provides a solid mathematical ground for medical practice based on previous practice expertise. However, the present criteria for accepting a symptom as an indication for a Homoeopathic medicine are fundamentally wrong. According to Bayes theorem these criteria should be based on relative occurrence instead of absolute occurrence. Bayesian theorem can be applied in retrospective research and in validation of Materia medica with successful cases using consensus procedure¹³

The research we need should be accepted in conventional diagnosis research. Like all kinds of research, we will have to deal with possible bias; like our reference standard: what is a good result? Symptoms should be defined more accurately, etcetera. These problems have been neglected in the past. We must realize that this research is meant to improve homeopathy, not to prove it. However, improved homeopathy will render better proof.

Homoeopathic doctors must be involved in validating Homoeopathic Materia Medica and Repertories because their cases are the basic material. This is possible if we are familiar with the basic principles of science and statistics. We must realize that their practice experience has scientific value if assessed properly. This can form the basis of drug validation and evidence so generated across the globe by multiple prescribers can be stronger and more meaningful than present Rates. Adopting Bayesian methodology opens the possibility of investigating homeopathy in everyday practice and of describing some aspects of homeopathy in conventional terms¹⁴

Future possibilities of symptom assessment:

Assessment of homeopathic symptoms becomes a necessity if we want to apply Bayes' theorem in homeopathy, but there are limitations as to feasibility. The essence is that we use the prevalence of symptoms instead of absolute occurrence. There are several ways to estimate this prevalence; there are retrospective methods like consensus meetings and analysis of practice registrations, but prospective assessment is generally considered to be the best method.¹⁵ The prospective assessment requires discipline, adequate software, sufficient doctors following roughly the same method, prepared to discuss their personal opinions, and commitment to sustain the effort for a period of three years. Not all symptoms are eligible for prospective research. The prevalence in the research population should be enough to acquire sufficient numbers. This depends on the inflow of new patients. A prevalence above 2% seems appropriate.¹² Symptoms with higher prevalence should have priority for this kind of assessment; they constitute the larger repertory rubrics that are most polluted by 'mere chance entries'. On the other hand, symptoms with a prevalence above 25% are not interesting for homeopathy because LR cannot be higher than 4, even if all patients of the corresponding medicine population have that symptom. The most eligible symptoms to assess are the so-called keynotes of the Materia medica; these are symptoms characteristic for the medicine with higher prevalence. These are the symptoms we use every day to detect or confirm our medicines.

DISCUSSION:

Homoeopathy has a unique opportunity to develop its own scientific identity in achieving evidence-based personalized medicine while RCT evidence fails to serve the needs of the individual patient. We can use accepted scientific methods derived from diagnosis research. There is a growing awareness that prognosis is more relevant than diagnosis. The prognosis (consistent with diagnosis) is a probability that the medicine will work, not a certainty that it works better than a placebo in the average patient. For assessing probabilities, we need other scientific tools than for hypothesis testing. We can apply Bayes' theorem for this purpose, which is rapidly recognized in all fields of science and incorporated in many computer programs, especially expert systems. There is a growing awareness that Bayes' theorem is a leading principle in medical knowledge. Applying Bayes' theorem in

Homoeopathy is straightforward: We have to assess the prevalence of Homoeopathic symptoms in our whole population and in populations responding well to specific Homoeopathic medicines. Defining the populations that respond well to specific medicines is still a challenge. We are in the process of adapting existing tools for establishing a causal relationship between effect and Homoeopathic medicine. Being aware of the problem of causality and getting used to more systematic evaluation of causality is an essential part of our scientific development.

CONCLUSION:

Introducing LR to the repertory will not only change its content but also its use. Because of the altered use we should consider structural updating. Entries of medicines in the repertory must reflect the importance of the symptom in relation to the remedy, not the occurrence of the symptom in proving and casuistry. This new repertory will increase usefulness and reliability, especially of large rubrics. It will enable us to make more reliable predictions about the number of symptoms we need in one case and the curative potential of medicine.

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